

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Malate by Aqueous Iodine Induced by Manganese (VII)

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The reaction of malate with aqueous iodine is slow in the absence of Mn (VII). Manganese (VII) increases the rate of reaction. The induction factor, $(I_0)/(Mn(VII))$ of this reaction at pH-4.15 is found to be less than unity (i.e., 0.5). The rate increases with the increase in malate and Mn (II) concentration, temperature and pH. First order rate constants decrease with time since Mn (VII) concentration decreases with the progress of the reaction. A mechanism for the induced action of Mn (VII) has been suggested.

OXIDATION of malic acid has been studied by various workers¹⁻³. Wieland and Franke⁴ have reported the oxidation of malic acid by hydrogen peroxide in the presence of Fe²⁺. Aqueous iodine and potassium permanganate have been used as oxidants by Kurian and Ghosh^{5,6} for the oxidation of dicarboxylic and hydroxy acids in presence of Co (III) as inductor. Kalra and Ghosh⁷ have studied the induced oxidation of oxalate, tartrate and citrate in the presence of Mn (VII) and (III).

In the present communication the oxidation of malate by aqueous iodine induced by Mn (VII) has been investigated.

Experimental

Materials: All the chemicals used were of B.D.H., A.R. quality and the solutions of all the reactants were prepared in bidistilled water. Malic acid, potassium bicarbonate, potassium permanganate and aqueous iodine were standardised before their use⁷

Kinetic procedure: All solutions were brought to the thermostat temperature and mixed in the reaction vessel, coated with black Japan, also previously thermostated. Aliquots were withdrawn at definite intervals of time, the reaction was quenched by addition of aliquots in the ice, prepared from distilled water, and the iodine was titrated against standard hypo, using starch as indicator. As malate was present in large excess, first order constants with respect to iodine have been calculated with reference to the first titre value.

Malate-malic acid mixtures of various pHs were obtained by adding the requisite quantity of potassium bicarbonate to a standard malic acid solution so that the concentration of the total reductant, viz., malic acid and malate was kept the same. pH values of reaction mixtures were measured with Beckman pH-meter using glass and calomel electrodes. The concentration of malate was assumed to be

equivalent to the concentration of potassium bicarbonate added to malic acid. Since the reaction between iodine and malate took place in dark even in the absence of Mn(VII), some experiments on the rate of uninduced reaction were performed under identical conditions.

Results

Effect of manganese (VII) concentration on rate
The rate of the reaction increases with the increase in the concentration of manganese (VII). However, this increase does not follow a linear relationship (cf. Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF MANGANESE (VII) CONCENTRATION ON RATE

[Malic acid] : $5 \times 10^{-2} M$	[Potassium Malate] : $5 \times 10^{-2} M$
[Iodine] : $6.35 \times 10^{-4} M$	pH : 4.15 Temp : 30°
KMnO ₄ × 10 ⁵ M	k × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
Nil	47.2
10.0	71.7
15.0	81.2
20.0	91.2

Effect of pH on rate: It is seen from Table 2 that the rate increases with the increase in pH of malate solution.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF pH ON RATE

[Reductant] : $10 \times 10^{-2} M$	Potassium permanganate : $20 \times 10^{-5} M$
[Iodine] : $6.35 \times 10^{-4} M$	Temp. : 30°
pH	k × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
3.1	21.7
3.5	41.2
3.8	54.2
4.15	91.2

Effect of reductant concentration on rate: The values of the quotents (first order constants, k,

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divided by the respective reductant concentration) recorded in Table 3 show that the reaction is also first order with respect to reductant. Thus, the total order of the reaction is found to be 2, though the first order constants with respect to iodine fall with time.

TABLE 3—CONSTANCY OF QUOTIENT $k/[\text{REDUCTANT}]$ AT 30° AND $p\text{H}=4.15$

$[\text{Reductant}] \times 10^2 M$	5.0	10.0
$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	44.1	86.4
$k/[\text{Reductant}]$	8.82	8.64

Effect of temperature on rate : The reaction was studied at two temperatures (i.e., 20° and 30°). The temperature coefficient and energy of activation of this reaction are found to be 2.04 and 12600 cal respectively.

Effect of bivalent manganese on rate : A perusal of the Table 4 indicates that the rate of the reaction increases with the increase in the concentration of Mn (II).

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF MANGANESE (II) CONCENTRATION ON RATE

$[\text{Reductant}] : 10 \times 10^{-2} M$; $[\text{Iodine}] : 6.35 \times 10^{-4} M$
 $[\text{Potassium permanganate}] : 20 \times 10^{-5} M$, $p\text{H} : 4.15$
 Temp. : 30°

$[\text{Manganous Sulphate}] \times 10^3 M$	$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
Nil	91.2
25.0	97.7
50.0	103.0
75.0	109.0

Discussion

It is a well known fact that when potassium permanganate is reacted with tartrate, citrate and malate etc. in the light, the pink colour of permanganate is quickly discharged and it is reduced to lower valent manganese^{5,6}. The rate of formation of free radicals of anions of tartrate, citrate and oxalate when permanganate reacts with them is faster in light than in the dark.

We have observed that the rate of the reaction of malate with aqueous iodine increases considerably in dark with the introduction of dilute potassium permanganate in the system. As Mn(VII) passes to Mn(II) by its reduction with an organic acid, free radicals of organic anion are generated as the change in the valency of manganese occurs by either one electron transfer or at the most a two electron transfer at a stage⁷. Hence with potassium permanganate there are several states of reduction of Mn(VII) to Mn(II) and we may have several free radicals produced in the system. The probable mechanism may be suggested for malate-iodine reaction induced by Mn(VII). Thus, higher valent

manganese first reacts with malate anion to give free radical :

where 'n' is the number of oxidation state of manganese ranging from 7+ to 2+. A half oxidised malate free radical thus generated in the system may be utilised by iodine to produce atomic iodine. Thus :

The generation of OH· may also be possible by the action of water on higher valent manganese according to the scheme :

The radical OH· may generate the free radical of the organic anion as :

It will be now interesting to compare this mechanism with those of several workers⁵⁻⁹.

In agreement with the experimental results, the sum of the reactions involved in the chain, excluding initiation and termination reactions, provides stoichiometric relationship of equation :

The chain termination reactions yield additional evidence in support of the mechanism advanced here as will be shown from our subsequent considerations. The steady state concentrations of $[\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_5^{1-}]$ and $[\text{I} \cdot]$ as obtained by usual methods lead to a expression :

$$\frac{[\text{I}]}{[\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_5^{1-}]} = \frac{k_2[\text{I}_2]}{k_3[\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_5^{2-}]} \frac{v_3}{v_2} \dots (a)$$

where v_1, v_2, v_3 etc. are the respective velocities of the reactions 1, 2, 3 etc.

and

$$v_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{v_1}{2} + \left(\frac{v_1^2}{4} + 2k_6v_1 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \dots (b)$$

$$v_3 = 2k_6v_1 \dots (c)$$

where

$$k_6 = \frac{k_2 k_3}{k_4} [\text{I}_2] [\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_5^{2-}] \dots (d)$$

and

$$v_1 = k_1 [\text{Mn}^{n+}] / [\text{H}^+] \dots (e)$$

It is evident from equation (a) that as the ratio $[I_2]/[C_4H_4O_5^{2-}]$ increases the stationary concentration of atomic iodine will increase relative to that of $[C_4H_4O_5^{1-}]$. On the basis of such considerations⁹ we would expect the chain breaking by the association of two atomic iodine (step 5) to become important. As the ratio $[I_2]/[C_4H_4O_5^{2-}]$ increases to sufficiently high value, step (5) will dominate and compete with step (3), which generates the radical $C_4H_4O_5^{1-}$ after reaction (2) consuming the $C_4H_4O_5^{1-}$ obtained in step (1). Apart from this effect, the retarding effect on step (3) due to the increase in $[H^+]$ ion concentration too will add to the accumulation of atomic iodine in the system and the consequent loss of this active species by reaction (5). Thus, when pH is low and hence the ratio $[I_2]/[C_4H_4O_5^{2-}]$ is high and v_3 low, reaction (5) is to be expected to dominate so that hardly may any chain be expected to propagate. This explains the low reaction rate at low pH. At lower $[I_2]/[C_4H_4O_5^{2-}]$ ratio the important chain termination reaction is (4) and is substantiated by high induction factor observed at higher pH (i.e., 4-15).

The initial rapid reduction of iodine is mainly due to the fast reactions (1) and (2). A reaction scheme consisting of the reactions (1), (2), (3) and (4) in which reaction (3) is assumed to be the rate determining reaction and (4), the important chain termination reaction at low $[I_2]/[C_4H_4O_5^{2-}]$ ratio, leads to the rate equation :

$$\frac{-d[I_2]}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{v_1^2}{4} + 2k_6v_2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{v_1}{2} \right] \quad \dots (f)$$

From (f) it follows that the reduction of iodine is a function of v_1 which has a high velocity, and that so long as v_1 is involved in the reaction, the reduction of iodine should naturally be very fast.

The kinetics of the reduction of iodine by malate in presence of Mn(VII) recorded herein, relates to the regular reaction that follows after the rapid initial consumption of iodine, when the chain breaking steps (4) and (5) are not significant to any appreciable extent. It is, therefore, obvious that for the portion of the reaction of which the rate constants have been recorded, step (3) is the rate determining one when step (2) is a fast one, as is to be understood

from the initial rapid loss of iodine. This leads to the rate relation :

$$\frac{-d[I_2]}{dt} = k_2k_2k_1[Mn(VII)][I_2][C_4H_4O_5^{2-}] \quad \dots (g)$$

where it has been assumed that

$$[C_4H_4O_5^{1-}] = k_1[Mn(VII)]$$

and hence

$$[I] = k_2k_1[Mn(VII)][I_2]$$

This is in harmony with the experimental findings.

We find the activation energy for the over all reaction to be about 12600 cal. The activation energy for the reaction (4) is expected to be small. Hence an activation energy of about 12600 cal may be attributed to two reactions noted in steps (2) and (3). Thus the activation energy for each step is comparable to the activation energies, which are usually less than 10000 cal¹⁰ and more frequently between 3000 and 6000 cal for free radical reactions.

The increase in the rate by Mn(II) is attributed to the oxidation of Mn(II) by Mn(VII) to Mn(III) which is also a strong oxidant. Mn(III) forms a complex with malate¹.

One of the products of this reaction identified by DNP(2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine) and Schiff's reagent tests was aldehyde.

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